

Real time air pollution modeling and dissemination of location based information using mobile devices

Final report submitted to
Natural Resource Data Management System
Department of Science and Technology, New Delhi

Real time air pollution modeling and dissemination of location based information using mobile devices

Final Report

Ref. No.NRDMS/11/1919/012(C)

Submitted to
Natural Resource Data Management System
Department of Science and Technology, New Delhi

By
Nishadh K A¹, P A Azeez¹ and R Mohanraj²

¹ Salim Ali Centre for Ornithology and Natural History
Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu

² Department of Environmental Management,
Bharthidasan University, Tiruchy, Tamil Nadu

April 2015

Contents

Project completion report	i
Executive summary	vii
Acknowledgments	ix
1 Project background	1
2 Development of real time particulate pollution monitor	3
2.1 Introduction	3
2.2 Materials and Methods	3
2.2.1 Air Quality Egg	4
2.2.2 Chromatic modulation based particulate monitor	4
2.2.3 Customization of Dylos™pro air quality monitor	5
2.2.4 Data validation and co-location sampling	6
2.3 Results and Discussion	6
2.3.1 Real time air quality monitor	6
2.3.2 Field deployment	7
2.3.3 Data validation and co-location sampling	10
2.4 Conclusion	11
3 Sensor observation service for real time particulate pollution monitors	12
3.1 Introduction	12
3.2 Materials and methods	13
3.2.1 Sensor Observation Service(SOS) specifications	13
3.2.2 Web map application for Sensor Observation Service	14
3.3 Results and discussion	14
3.3.1 Sensor Observation Service implementation	14
3.3.2 Web map application for SOS implementation	14
3.4 Conclusion	18
4 Web application to visualize mobile particulate pollution monitoring	19
4.1 Introduction	19
4.2 Materials and Methods	19
4.3 Results and Discussion	21
4.4 Conclusion	22
5 Real time particulate pollution modelling for Coimbatore region using WRF-CHEM	23
5.1 Introduction	23
5.2 Materials and Methods	23

5.2.1	WRF-CHEM model environment set-up	23
5.2.2	Model domain and parameter for Coimbatore area	24
5.2.3	Script for real time running of WRF-CHEM	24
5.3	Results and Discussion	25
5.4	Conclusion	27
6	Web visualization of WRF-CHEM model output	28
6.1	Introduction	28
6.2	Materials and Methods	28
6.2.1	WRF-CHEM output into JSON	28
6.2.2	Web map application for WRF-CHEM output	29
6.3	Results and Discussion	29
6.4	Conclusion	31
7	Anthropogenic emission inventory for particulate pollutants in Coimbatore region	32
7.1	Introduction	32
7.2	Materials and methods	32
7.3	Study area:	32
7.3.1	Emission source and activity data	33
7.3.2	Emission factors, calculation and spatial allocation	36
7.4	Results and Discussion	39
7.4.1	Anthropogenic PM _{2.5} emission from different sectors of Coimbatore region	39
7.4.2	Anthropogenic PM ₁₀ emission from different sectors of Coimbatore region	39
7.5	Conclusion	43
8	Inter comparison of emission inventories and evaluation of WRF-CHEM output for Coimbatore domain	44
8.1	Introduction	44
8.2	Materials and methods	44
8.2.1	Emission inventory (EI) Inter comparison	44
8.2.2	WRF-CHEM output evaluation	45
8.3	Results and Discussions	45
8.3.1	Emission inventory (EI) inter-comparison	45
8.3.2	WRF-CHEM output evaluation	47
8.3.3	Conclusion	48
9	Mobile application for location specific particulate pollution information	49
9.1	Introduction	49
9.2	Materials and Methods	49
9.2.1	Client side Android application	49
9.2.2	Server side program	49
9.3	Results and Discussion	51
9.3.1	Client side Android application	51
9.3.2	Server side program	51
9.4	Conclusion	51

Executive summary

Particulate matter (dust) air pollution is a serious environmental and health concern in the fast growing urban areas of India. It involves multi level interacting components of emission sources, dynamism of atmosphere and implications on public health and environment. Mitigation or management of this problem requires information, realistic models and predictability on the levels of pollution with adequate temporal and spatial resolution. Establishment of urban area real time monitoring and modeling system is inevitability and it is being recognized as a vital infrastructure for addressing the problem in various locations of the country. However, with ever-increasing necessity for sensor networks, huge capital and recurring expenditure for the real time modeling system in terms of computational resources are hampering wider installation of such systems. Technical hurdles such as inherent variability and lack of an appropriate bridge system that is interoperable and facilitates optimal usage with access of real-time data are further hampering efficiency and robustness of these systems in deriving information and its dissemination. On the other hand, there is a growing realization that a low cost monitoring network with modeling environment would be an important enabler for high spatial resolution air pollution observations and related applications. There are evidences from field trails, showing that low cost sensors with advanced calibration techniques would be an important asset for real time air pollution monitoring. However, it involves a huge challenge in terms of fine-tuning the sensing technology, data management, networks sustenance and derivation of suitable application from the collected information.

The project in Coimbatore, a fast growing urban conglomerate in the state of Tamil Nadu (India), intended to address the question of how disparate and meager sensor resource's real time data can be better organized, modeled and disseminated for integrated management of particulate matter air pollution. The project applied Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) Sensor Web Enablement (SWL) specifications. The specifications such as Sensor Observation Services (SOS), Web Processing Services (WPS) and GeoSMS were approached for organizing sensor resources, real time air quality modeling and its data dissemination. The main objective of the project was to

i) Develop Sensor Observation Service for spatially distributed air quality sensors and real time meteorological data website. ii) Develop Real time air quality modeling web processing service using the SOS, validate and compare it with similar other models. iii) Develop a Geo-SMS based android application to disseminate the modeling result.

To address the objective one, the project developed a low cost real time particulate matter monitor by combining Dylos™pro, a commodity indoor air quality monitor, single board computer and real time data communication system. Field trials of the developed monitors was tested in four locations of the Coimbatore urban area and found its suitability in real time particulate pollution monitoring. To test the robustness of data communication, two mode of data transfer through SMS and REST API were tested and found to have satisfactory functionality. The Sensor observation service was enabled for these established monitors using istSOS, a python based implementation of OGC SOS. To demonstrate the functionality of the SOS implementation, a web application was devel-

oped which consume the SOS as data back-end. Data download in different interoperable formats, visualization of time series data from the real time monitor in chart and table view are some of the functionalities enabled along with the web application.

To address the objective two, WRF-CHEM based real time particulate pollution modeling system was developed. A python based automatic execution script was developed to make the modeling system to execute in real time. To address the high computational requirement of WRF-CHEM simulation in real time, different computer processor inter-comparison was carried out. Thus, we found satisfactory usability of cloud computer clusters in time bound simulation of the WRF-CHEM for Coimbatore urban domain. As alternative to cloud computers, the project also experimented with low cost, low energy demand single board computer cluster such as ARM processor based Cubietruck cluster. It was found that although the WRF-CHEM can be made into effective functioning system using this computer processor, the time required for the simulation is considerably higher than other computer systems. To enable the Web Processing Services (WPS) for the model output, a web application was developed to visualize WRF-CHEM output in interoperable interface with functionality similar to the OGC standard WPS. For addressing basic requirements of WRF CHEM simulation, a high resolution emission inventory (1X1 km) for anthropogenic particulate pollutants PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ was developed covering 3000 sq.km of Coimbatore and its adjacent regions. Secondary information from multiple government agencies and sources were also used for estimating the particulate pollution emission from Coimbatore region considering 2012 as base year. In validating the WRF-CHEM output, it is found that the simulation results are not akin to the observations and need further sensitivity study with various micro physics and other atmospheric chemistry options of WRF CHEM for Coimbatore domain.

To address the objective three of the project a GeoSMS backed Android mobile application was developed. The application was developed based on an offline map that had functionality to send an SMS containing user's current location coordinates on touch map clicking. To provide the server side functionality for the mobile application, a SMS gateway was setup in the server side backed with nearest neighbourhood algorithm KD-tree. The algorithm access the WRF-CHEM model output and provides the location based information according to the received GeoSMS bearing location coordinates of the user.

By adopting open source specification implementation the study intends to develop "best practice" to organize real time data on particulate pollution in Coimbatore urban area. The project foresees better management of real time particulate pollution data from monitoring and modeling output with extensible and interoperable data format. The main output of the project is successful demonstrations of time and space relevant data provision for solving the particulate pollution problems of Coimbatore, as an example replicable elsewhere.

Acknowledgments

The project was funded by Natural Resource Data Management System (NRDMS), National Spatial Data Infrastructure(NSDI), Department of Science and Technology (DST), Government of India. We express our heartfelt gratitude to NRDMS,NSDI, DST for their financial support. We are grateful to Dr P S Acharya (NRDMS, DST) for kind encouragement, guidance and coordination for successful completion of the project.

We are thankful to Dr.Ram Pratab Singh (SACON) for his help in setting up cloud computer services. We are thankful to Mr C V Jayaprakash (PSG College of Arts & Sciences, Coimbatore), Mr R Mohanraj (Coimbatore Wetlands, Coimbatore), Mr Kalidas (OSAI, Coimbatore) and Abdul Rasheed (Coimbatore) for their help in establishing and maintaining the field stations of real time air quality monitors in various parts of Coimbatore. We are grateful to Mr.Chandra Sekaran, Engineer at Tamil Nadu Pollution Control Board for his help rendered during the project period.

We are thankful to Ms Aswathy P V for her assistance relating to the project. We are thankful to Mr Jayakumar R and team in the administrative division, Mr Aneesh Abraham and team in the finance Division and Mr Vythiyanathan of SACON for their support and prompt helps. We are thankful to Mr Sreenivasan, computer assistant at SACON for his timely helps.

We are grateful to the community behind the open source code / applications used in the project hosted at Github or elsewhere and electronic suppliers for their help in clarification and assistance. The community at 52°N and IstsSOS helped in smooth setting up and extension of Sensor Observation Services. We are thankful to authors of QualitySchue web application used as front end for SOS. Workshop conducted by simple labs, Chennai gave us the drive in developing the real time air quality monitor and its field deployment. The custom control box developed by M/s HB Power System (Coimbatore) aided in safe field deployment of real time particulate monitors.

We express our gratitude to the author of WRF-EMS program Mr Robert Rozumalski, for gentle introduction to the WRF modeling system. We are grateful to Michel Mesquita, author of eWRF program for basic introduction and online course on WRF. Mr John Robert Lawson, author of lazy WRF program aided in developing the automatic script for WRF-CHEM execution. Mr Arif, author of pyWRFChemEmiss, is gratefully acknowledged for insightful discussions on WRF- CHEM cloud computer execution. We are thankful to the participants at WRF-forum for their revealing discussion on running the WRF CHEM model. Numerous blog authors on WRF CHEM, especially Mr Sergio Ibarra Espinosa for his article on WRF CHEM compilation is thankfully acknowledged. The article on WRF compilation with testing put up by NCAR in WRF official web site greatly eased and solved errors in WRF CHEM compilation. We are thankful to Mr Cameron Beccario, author of Tokyo air web application, which is used for visualizing the WRF CHEM output. We are thankful to Mr Stacy Walters, NCAR for help in compiling Anthro-emiss, a WRF-CHEM emission inventory preprocessor program. We are thankful to officials at Census of India, Tamil Nadu State Transport Corporation (TNSTC), Coimbatore Regional Transport Offices and Tamil Nadu Pollution Control Board (TNPCB),

and author of way2cbe.com for their help in collecting the data for emission inventory preparation. We express our gratitude to Mr Hisham Ghosheh (Offline map), Android tutorials cs76.net and the IITM-K that organized advanced android workshop. Their assistance was immensely important for the development of Android application.

The project team is indebted to the Scientists and Researchers of SACON for insightful discussions, and down-to-earth but discerning inquiries that strengthened our work greatly. We were privileged to be in their ingenious company.

Chapter 1

Project background

Particulate air pollution is a major public health problem in India. Global burden of Disease (2012) report points out that in India premature deaths caused due to air pollution has increased six times than the level in the year 2000. The report also points out that outdoor air pollution is one among the five major causes of deaths in India. The latest World Health Organization (2014) study on particulate pollution level in global cities shows that more than 80 percent of cities, which are monitoring the pollution level fail with respect to the stipulated guidelines of safe pollution levels. The Indian cities are ranked high in deviations from the guidelines. These reports highlights the urgent need of managing the particulate pollution to avoid undue cost in terms of people's health.

Mitigation or management of the predicament requires information, realistic models and predictability on the levels of pollution with adequate temporal and spatial resolution. Establishment of urban area real time monitoring and modeling system is inevitability and it is being recognized as a vital infrastructure for addressing the problem in disparate locations of the country. However, with ever-increasing necessity for sensor networks, huge capital and recurring expenditure for the real time modeling system in terms of computational resources are hampering wider installation of such systems.

Technical hurdles such as inherent variability and lack of an appropriate bridge system that is interoperable and facilitates optimal usage with access of real-time data are further hampering efficiency and robustness of these systems in deriving information and its dissemination. On the other hand, there is a growing realization that a low cost monitoring network with modeling environment would be an important enabler for high spatial resolution air pollution observations and related applications. There are evidences from field trails, showing that low cost sensors with advanced calibration techniques would be an important asset for real time air pollution monitoring. However, it involves a huge challenge in terms of fine-tuning the sensing technology, data management, networks sustenance and derivation of suitable application from the collected information. Similarly, for real time air quality modeling, application of cloud computer resources with local level prediction would increase the usability of model output for deriving the time and space relevant pollution level for awareness and policy intervention measures.

The present project was conceived with the contextual objective of exploring such systems in addressing increasingly serious air pollution issues. In specifics, the project in urban Coimbatore, a fast growing urban conglomerate in the state of Tamil Nadu, India, intended to address the question of how disparate and meagre sensor resource's real time data can be better organized, modelled and disseminated for integrated management of particulate matter air pollution. The project applied Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) Sensor Web Enablement (SWE) specifications. The specifications such as Sensor Observation Services (SOS), Web-Processing Services (WPS) and GeoSMS were approached

for organizing sensor resources, real time air quality modeling and its data dissemination. The main objective of the project was to

1. Develop Sensor Observation Service for spatially distributed air quality sensors and real time meteorological data website.
2. Develop Real time air quality modeling web processing service using the SOS, validate and compare it with similar other models.
3. Develop a Geo-SMS based android application to disseminate the modeling result.

The following chapters discuss in sequence the developments to achieve the above objectives.

Chapter 2

Development of real time particulate pollution monitor

2.1 Introduction

Particulate matter in air has serious health effects. Real time monitoring of these pollutants have huge potential in providing relevant health advisories and enforcing time bound regulatory measures. High upfront and running costs for the monitors currently in use largely hinders their wide deployment to meet the requirements of adequate spatial and temporal resolution. The current project in view of this limitation taking it as an opportunity in physical computing has conceived experimentation with low cost operated sensors and derivative monitors for real time particulate matter monitoring. It in fact was to try out simple gadgets for the purpose. Recent studies have shown the usefulness of low cost monitor for particulate and other air pollutant sampling. Northcross et al.,[1] tried out Dylos™ air quality monitor in particulate sampling and showed its effectiveness comparable to high-end standard regulatory monitors. Holstius et al and Gao et.al [2, 3] demonstrated much cheaper commodity dust samplers as effective particulate monitors. Such studies encouraged the growing perception to replace the current state of relying on high cost pollution monitors, with much more cheaper, but effectual, and accessible systems.

The current chapter addresses the major component in objective one of the project, to develop Sensor Observation Service (SOS) for spatially distributed air quality sensors and real time meteorological data website. By developing a real time particulate pollution monitor, it offers a candidature for spatially distributed air quality sensors for applying sensor observation services.

2.2 Materials and Methods

Essentially, the project deliberates upon the usability of low cost, simple sensor systems for real time particulate matter air pollution monitoring and modeling. The project considered three major alternatives for development of the particulate monitor, Viz., i) Community developed air pollution monitor, the “Air-Quality-Egg”, ii) Chromatic modulation based dust monitor, and iii) Customization of Dylos™ pro indoor air quality monitor as real time outdoor monitor. The robustness and published past studies with the Dylos™ air quality monitor made us to choose it as base sampler for current development of real time particulate matter monitor for wider deployment.

Figure 2.1: The air quality egg sensing component

Figure 2.2: Chromatic modulation based particulate matter, design and prototype

2.2.1 Air Quality Egg

It is an open, community led, and community funded project aiming to set-up distributed real-time air quality sensor Networks[4]. It comprised of outdoor sensor board which holds relevant air pollution sensors, one separate egg shaped wireless router (indoor usage) to receive the acquired data from the sensor board and transmit it to the ‘Internet of things’ web service ‘cosm.com’ through Ethernet/ wireless modem. The image 2.1 reproduced shows the “Air-Quality-Egg” sensing component.

Initially for us the community developed “Air-Quality-Egg” was the choice sensor system for the project. However, to procure the gadget during further deliberations with its manufactures, we found that the specifications for sensing particulate matter pollution was still under development and the model that they were marketing is yet to be equipped for our specific measurements / requirements. The gadget was concentrating only on gaseous pollutants. Hence, we had to shelve further review or deployment of the “Air-Quality-Egg” based monitor for the present project.

2.2.2 Chromatic modulation based particulate monitor

Technological developments in micro-electro-mechanical systems provides huge cost reduction in instrument components used for monitors based on optical sensing and lead the way for much inexpensive chromatic modulation (color variation) based monitors. Several recent studies have shown how promising are the features of those kind of low cost monitors in particulate and black carbon monitoring [5, 6]. We made an initial design and basic prototype of a low cost real time monitor for particulate and black carbon by coupled dust sensor and chromatic modulation technique. The image 2.2 shows the design and prototype of the chromatic modulation based monitor. The monitor comprised of i) a rotational 10 micrometer particulate filter equipped with a web camera facing the filter

Table 2.1: Features of Dylos™DC1100 air quality monitor and other commercially available real time particulate matter monitor (From [7] table 3.2)

Sensor	Measurement principle	Accuracy	Precision	Limit of detection	Cost
DC1100 Air Quality Monitor	Dylos Corp.	No data	15% collocated	0.5 μm	<300 US\$
831 Aerosol Mass Monitor	MetOne	10% to calibration aerosol	No data	0.5 m	<2000 US\$
Personal DataRAM Model pDR-1500	Thermo Scientific	5% of reading precision	0.2% of reading or 0.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ 360-s avg	0.1 μm	5500 US\$
microAeth® Model AE51	AethLabs Black Carbon	no standard	0.1 μg BC/ m^3 360-s avg	<0.16 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	6000 US\$

to capture the dust accumulation for chromatic modulation analysis, ii) a column with dust sensor and light source, iii) a vacuum air pump and iv) an Arduino board to program the whole monitoring process and communicate the data on real time basis. The major change in this design is the coupling of optical property differentiation, chromatic modulation technique in single platform and introduction of a provision for invasive sampling (if required) features for particulate monitoring. The dust sensor, Sharp-GP2Y1010AU0F, is based on optical sensing which measures the quantity of particles by reflected infrared rays on phototransistors from the dust column. From the initial prototype, it is found that the development and field deployment demand significant time and finance which exceeded the current scope of project. That made us to review the gadget further to find a suitable particulate monitor. A probable candidate was Dylos™pro air quality monitor.

2.2.3 Customization of Dylos™pro air quality monitor

Dylos™DC1100 pro air quality monitor is a laser particle counter, giving time bound measures of two size range (<0.5 and <2.5 micrometer) particles on an inbuilt LCD screen, to be transmitted to a computer through a serial plug. It is widely used for indoor air quality monitoring for air purifiers and particulate monitoring. The system, an inherently indoor one, was found to be useful and the data reliable in outdoor conditions as well in a study[1] by University of California Berkeley. The table 2.1 compares the features of Dylos™pro air quality monitor with other commercially available particulate matter monitor with cost details.

To customize it to the local weather conditions necessary changes were made. It was also equipped for storing and transferring the data to convert it into a real time monitor. It was having serial connection port, and the same was used to connect with low cost single board computer Raspberry pi for real time data communication from the monitor to the central server. A Linux Debian based Raspberry pi computer was enabled with a GSM data card and it was programmed to communicate between the device and the server using the SMS gateway Gammu and Crontab. Thus, the Raspberry pi computer connected to the monitor can send by SMS the sample data to a central server at an interval of 15 minutes. The interval was fixed considering that limit per day for SMS was

Figure 2.3: Dylos™ air quality monitor and Raspberry pi single board computer

100 from a single GSM SIM card. The image 2.3 shows the components of Dylos™ based real time particulate matter monitor.

2.2.4 Data validation and co-location sampling

The Dylos™ air quality monitor provide data (counts) for particulate matter in size ranges of $<2.5 \mu\text{g}$ and $<0.5 \mu\text{g}$ per 0.01 ft^3 . These counts have to be converted into mass values such as $2.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ or $10 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to compare with the regulatory units. Similar study [8] carried out using Dylos™ and calibrating it with standard particulate monitor provided a method to convert the counts from Dylos™ into particulate mass data. The conversion is carried out by following equation

$$PM \text{ concentration}(\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3) = \text{Number of particles} * 3531.5 * \text{Particle mass}$$

The equation is based on approximation, considering particles shape in sampling environment as spherical, with a density of $1.65 \text{E-}12 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ [9], radius of a particle in the PM2.5 channel as $0.44 \mu\text{m}$ [10], radius of a particle in the PM10 channel as $2.60 \mu\text{m}$ [10] and mass of a particle in the PM2.5 channel and PM10 channel as $5.89 \text{E-}7 \mu\text{g}$ and $1.21 \text{E-}4 \mu\text{g}$ respectively. A value of 3531.5 was used to convert the sample orifice size of Dylos™ monitor in 0.01 ft^3 to 1 m^3 . Since atmospheric humidity can significantly [8] influence the counts (reading) from laser based particulate matter monitors, a humidity correction factor was used to correct the output from the monitor. To ensure the reliability of the Dylos™ reading, a co-location sampling was carried out with industrially calibrated particulate monitor Aerocet 531S™. The data from Aerocet 531S™ and Dylos™ was compared to get their correlations.

2.3 Results and Discussion

2.3.1 Real time air quality monitor

Real time particulate matter monitor was developed by combining Dylos™ indoor particulate monitor with single board computer and a real time data communication system. The image 2.4 shows the hardware and software component of the monitor. The software part comprised of a serial reader that reads the data from Dylos™ into single board computer and saves it in *Sqlite* database for back up. The collected data was then communicated in real time by means of SMS and Representation State Transfer Application Programming Interface (REST-API). The sections A.1.1 and A.1.2 provides sample *Python* code used

Figure 2.4: Hardware and software components of the real time Dylos™ air quality monitor

Figure 2.5: Dylos™ air quality monitor field deployment casing

for above purposes. The field deployment of Dylos™ air quality monitor was done fixing a custom-made steel casing for the monitor. The image 2.5 shows the casing developed for Dylos™ air quality monitor. The casing provides all weather protection with adequate ventilation facility. The power supply to the monitor was provided by power plug connected to an inverter.

2.3.2 Field deployment

To assess the functionality of the developed air quality monitor, four customized monitors was deployed in various parts of Coimbatore city. The map 2.6 shows the locations of deployment. Table 2.2 gives details about stations for field deployment of the monitors. Heights for placing the monitor was chosen to ensure safety and protection of the monitor. The image 2.7 shows the temporal and average diurnal variability of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ in Thadagam station recorded by Dylos™ air quality monitor. The sampling station at Thadagam is situated in a large brick kiln cluster of Coimbatore. The diurnal peak of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} is an indicative of the emission from brick kiln industries active period of brick backing using firewood. The image 2.8 shows the particulate level reading at the station Kuniamuthur. As the station is situated in a residential area close to a main road and a busy high way, the pollutant concentration was changing with the diurnal activity in the surrounding areas.

Figure 2.6: The locations of DylosTM air quality monitor deployed stations

Table 2.2: The profile and period of sampling for DylosTM air quality monitor in different stations of Coimbatore

Station code	Station name	Monitor position height	Period of sampling
TDM	Thadagam	7 meter	24th January -28th March 2014
KNMR	Kuniamuthur	3 meter	6th-8th May & 14th-20th July 2014
SVNC	Sivnandha Colony	1.5 meter	17th April -05 May 2014
GVR	GV residency	7 meter	29-30 April 2014

Figure 2.7: Particulate pollutant recorded in Thadagam, Coimbatore by DylosTM air quality monitor

Figure 2.8: Particulate pollutant recorded in Kuniamuthur, Coimbatore by Dylos™ air quality monitor

Figure 2.9: Particulate pollutant recorded in Sivanandha Colony, Coimbatore by Dylos™ air quality monitor

Figure 2.10: Particulate pollutant recorded in GV Residency, Coimbatore by DylosTM air quality monitor

Figure 2.11: Line and correlation plot of particulate pollution reading from co-location sampling of DylosTM and Aerocet monitor

The image 2.9 shows the particulate pollution reading at the station Sivanandha Colony. As this station is closely situated nearby a busy main road, the readings especially PM10 are indicative of the traffic situation.

The image 2.10 shows the particulate pollution reading from the station GV residency.

2.3.3 Data validation and co-location sampling

The co-location sampling provided a measure to compare the DylosTM air quality monitor with industrially calibrated Aerocet 531STM monitor. This gives a method to ensure the validity of the data from DylosTM monitor. Co-location sampling was carried out during 14 - 18 January 2015. Considering the safety of the instruments the sampling was done between 9 am to 9 pm during all the days. The image 2.11 shows the line and correlation plot of the readings from DylosTM and Aerocet 531STM co-location sampling. It is observed that the reading from DylosTM for PM2.5 recorded highest correlation of 0.74 ($p < 0.01$) followed by PM10 with correlation coefficient of 0.52 ($p < 0.01$) against Aerocet 531STM readings.

The correlation of Dylos™ with Aerocet 531S™ for PM2.5 was comparable to the sampling accuracy of the earlier study [1] which recorded the correlation of 0.81-0.99 ($p < 0.01$) for Dylos™ pro air quality monitor against the industrial and regulatory grade samplers.

2.4 Conclusion

The study developed an outdoor real time particulate monitor using a customized low cost dust profiler Dylos™ pro air quality monitor. The initial field trials and validation studies has shown the promising efficacy of the low cost monitors in addressing the scarcity of particulate pollution levels data in second tier urban centers of India. This component of the project addressed objective of developing real time air quality monitors for enabling sensor observation services.

Chapter 3

Sensor observation service for real time particulate pollution monitors

3.1 Introduction

Integration of multi-source information to derive contextual knowledge is important in environmental management. Tools for integrating observations from multiple components of environment can significantly ease time and space related decision-making. Interoperability standard tools such as Sensor Observation Service (SOS) can provide the interface for orchestrating multi-source observations, promote data reuse and reduce unnecessary duplication of resources in cost-effective manner [11]. SOS is an important sensor web enablement specification evolved for interoperability of sensor observations for data aggregation from live, in-situ and remote sensors [12, 13]. It provides an accessible interface for sensors and sensor data archives for various processes in knowledge generation such as data analysis, modeling and information dissemination. Initiatives such as *Common Sense* [14] and Earth Observation, Environmental Modeling for the Mitigation of Health Risks (EO2HEAVEN) [15] demonstrate management of sensor resources in air quality monitoring. The project ‘Common Sense’ carried out by Intel Labs, Berkeley addresses the issues related to management of widely distributed and high spatial resolution sensor resources in urban spaces. EO2HEAVEN is an end-user oriented research aimed at better understanding of complex relationships between environmental changes and its impact on human health. Both the above initiatives explored the use of spatial information infrastructure compliant to Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) standards in integrating sensor observation from different domains of environmental health hazards to human exposure. By utilizing the power of flexibility in specifications of SOS, they demonstrate validation of health hazard model derived from various sensor observations to increase utility for the end user.

Particulate matter air pollution is a serious issue in fast growing urban areas of India [16]. It involves an array of issues - multi-level interacting components of emission sources, dynamism of atmosphere and implications on public health, ecosystems and environment [17]. Mitigation or management of this problem requires basic information and predictability on the levels of pollution with adequate temporal and spatial resolution. Urban area real time sensor networks are a necessity and are being considered as a basic infrastructure for addressing the problem in different parts of country [18]. However, with increasing necessity for real time sensor system, huge capital and recurring expenditure required for its establishment is hampering wider installation of such systems [19]. Technical hurdles such as inherent variability and lack of an appropriate bridge system that is interoperable and facilitates optimal usage and access of real-time data are hampering

Figure 3.1: The components of Sensor Observation Services

efficiency and robustness of these networks in deriving information and its dissemination [11]. On the other hand, there is a growing realization that a low cost monitoring network would be an important enabler in high spatial resolution air pollution observations and related applications [19, 20]. There are field trials that show the low cost sensors with advanced calibration techniques as an important asset for real time air pollution monitoring and management [1]. However, it is a huge challenge in terms of fine-tuning the sensor technology, data management, networks sustenance and development of suitable applications from the collected information [21].

This chapter addresses the second major component in the project objective of developing sensor observation service for real time particulate pollution monitor. The development of a web application integrating multiple sensor resources in a standard compliant SOS implementation and visualization platform was discussed.

3.2 Materials and methods

The web application was developed for particulate matter monitors in urban Coimbatore, a fast growing urban conglomerate located in the state of Tamil Nadu (India). For developing sensor observation services (SOS) for air quality monitor and meteorological web sites, the *Python* based SOS implementation *IstSOS* was used.

3.2.1 Sensor Observation Service(SOS) specifications

SOS specifications are information and service models for access and control of heterogeneous sensor resources. The image 3.1 shows the four components of the SOS. In the domain of air pollution, SOS specification standardizes data from distinct sensor resources to reduce disparity and improves interoperability of the sensors. In the current project, SOS specifications were used for organizing data collected from Dylos™ air quality monitors and meteorological data repository websites on Coimbatore geographical region. OGC SOS (standard version 1.0) based implementation, *IstSOS* was used [13] for the SOS. It provides interfaces to interact with sensor observations, sensors exploration, measurement retrieval, data management, transactional operations and dispatch of the raw data. *IstSOS* is written in *Python* programming language. It is based on the Apache web server, through *mod_python* package. It relies on PostgreSQL / PostGIS database for data storage and access. *IstSOS* uses GDAL library, Psycopg2 for database connections. This application was used as tool for organizing the data sources as API (Application Programming Interface) for the web application developed.

METEOROLOGICAL PARAMETERS The major challenge in managing the geo-spatial information concerning the air pollution is integration of location based data from various sources to derive relevant and time bound information. In our country, the challenge is greater for the existing lacunae in standards and Application Programming Interface (API) in real time data dissemination websites. Web extraction is to be a widely followed solution for this situation. It is a process of capturing data and extracting information from dynamic web sites for use in another context. Real time meteorological parameters are required for particulate matter dispersion and forecasting, important enablers in air pollution management. As of now, web applications automates extraction of such parameters and implements SOS on the real time meteorological data for Coimbatore region from Tamil Nadu Agriculture Weather Network maintained by Tamil Nadu Agriculture University (www.tawntnau.ac.in) and Weather underground web portal (www.wunderground.com).

3.2.2 Web map application for Sensor Observation Service

To demonstrate the effectiveness of sensor observation services, a web map application was integrated with *IstSOS* implementation for Dylos™air quality monitors and other meteorological data sources. This web application was developed based on existing source code of *qualitySCHU* [22] web application.

3.3 Results and discussion

3.3.1 Sensor Observation Service implementation

The data from Dylos™air quality monitors was integrated with SOS via a serial connection and networking with central server for real time updating of the SOS. As per the deployment situation either Internet FTP based networking or SMS based networking was used to communicate between server and monitor. For Internet based networking, the single board computer Raspberry pi connected with the Dylos™monitors was installed with a *bash daemon* script which links a *Python* script for serial reading of the monitored data. A GSM modem was installed with the Raspberry pi. The *Python* script also converts the readings from the monitor into a CSV file, which is in the form to be uploaded into the *IstSOS* insert observation framework. This is further transferred to central server using file transfer protocol and uploaded into the *IstSOS* using *CSV Python* importer. The image 3.2 shows various steps involved in SOS enablement of data from Dylos™air quality monitor. In case of GSM SMS based communication, GSM modem was used for sending SMS in which the *Python* script converts the serial reading from monitors into a SMS at every 15 minutes intervals. At the server side a *Python* script, supported by Gammu was used to manage the received SMS and to upload the data into the SOS. For meteorological web sites, sensor observation service was enabled with importing the collected data in *CSV* format into the *IstSOS*.The images 3.3 to 3.5 shows the various facilities provided by *IstSOS* for sensor observation services.

3.3.2 Web map application for SOS implementation

The web map application based on *qualitySchu* [22] open source comprised of a web map and various menu links, which provides for viewing the Sensor Observation Services in different formats. The image 3.6 shows the various processes and components involved in the web map application.

Figure 3.2: Steps in Sensor Observation Service integration for Dylos™ air quality monitors

Coimbatore air | IstSOS webadmin develop... | localhost/istsos/admin/ | Google

Server Services Data viewer | IstSOS

About IstSOS Status Database Service provider Service identification Coordinates system Get Observation Configuration Prtg Configuration New service Oulero service

Server Status

Summary of IstSOS instances and run-time status

Service	Features Of Im	Offerings	Procedures	Observed Prop	Availability	Database	GetCapabilities	DescribeSensor	GetObservation	GetFeaturesOfIm	InsertObservat	Register Sensor
awqcb	0	1	0	0	up	active	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
trou_cbe	13	2	14	10	up	active	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
coamcoam	0	0	0	4	up	active	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
dykacbe	1	1	1	4	up	active	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
demo	0	0	0	0	up	active	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
cbcd	2	1	2	2	up	active	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
trou	3	2	4	4	up	active	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Open Source Software by Institute of Earth Science - IISCI

Figure 3.3: *IstSOS* interface for adding the new procedure which describes about sensor resource and its meta information

Figure 3.4: IstSOS interface for editing the procedure

Figure 3.5: IstSOS interface for viewing the sensor observation reading in chart format

Figure 3.6: Various components and processes involved in web map application functioning

Figure 3.7: The web map front end of the web application

Figure 3.8: The table view of the sensor reading in the web application

Figure 3.9: The chart view of the sensor reading in the web application

The web application was mainly based on two JavaScript file namely map.js and menu.js. The section A.2.3 and A.2.4 shows the code of these files. The map.js is responsible to parse the SOS sensor services, take the latitude longitude from the SOS procedure and plot it as a map marker for each sensor. The image 3.7 shows the web-map front end of the web application.

The menu.js file oversees the API call from SOS instance with chosen sensor services. The API call is a *URL* command as shown in the below line.

```
1 http://localhost/istsos/wa/istsos/services/‘‘+selectedServiceToDownload  
+’’/operations/getobservation/offerings/temporary/procedures/‘‘+  
selectedProceduresToDownload+’’/observedproperties/‘‘+  
selectedObservedProperties+’’/eventtime/‘‘+  
selectedStartdateToDownload+’’/‘‘+selectedEnddateToDownload+’’;
```

The URL command parses the SOS instance for its particular sensor services, its procedure, observed properties with time for data request and data output in specific formats. The other functionality of web application was developed above the core *URL* based querying of SOS. The other functionality of the web application such as chart, table and data download functionality was enabled by linking with JavaScript libraries such as select.js for date range picker, canvas.js for chart or graph view of the sensor reading, bootstrap.js for front end of the web application. The images 3.8 and 3.9 shows the table and chart view of the sensor readings from SOS.

3.4 Conclusion

The chapter discussed the development of a web application directed towards integrating multi-domain sensor resources in standard compliant sensor observation platform. It discusses upon the utility of sensor resources for particulate matter air pollution monitoring, mitigation and management, implementation of sensor observation services for the sensor resources, and on the platform for visualizing the observations.

Chapter 4

Web application to visualize mobile particulate pollution monitoring

4.1 Introduction

Spatial variability assessment of pollution using mobile monitoring provides information on pollution level with respect to the specific location. It is important in understanding health impacts of air pollution and devising preventive measures for vulnerable population residing in intensive pollution zones [23]. This chapter aim to discuss the spatial variability of particulate pollution in Coimbatore area. Further, it discuss upon developing a web based interactive application for disseminating the mobile monitoring readings.

4.2 Materials and Methods

To assess the spatial variability of particulate pollution in Coimbatore urban region, hand-held real time particulate monitor, Aerocet 531S™ was used. It is a real-time photometric sampler (Met One Inc, 2014), that samples PM in a range of 1, 2.5, 4, 7, 10 μm in aerodynamic diameters of mass and count mode along with Total Suspended Particulates, Relative humidity and Temperature. Using right angle scattering method it counts the number of particulates in the air and by applying a proprietary algorithm on the counts, it estimates mass concentration of particulates. The reading by this technique can be influenced by high relative humidity [24]. As a correction factor, sample readings $>75\%$ was excluded.

Spatially disperse sampling was carried out by random point generation in the study area. The locations were then approached by a vehicle for sampling. During the sampling the vehicle was switched off for 3 minutes and duplicates of 1 minute sampling was carried out in each point. For the ease in the mobile sampling, the mobile particulate matter

Figure 4.1: The components of the mobile particulate monitor

Figure 4.2: The 1 km average values of particulate pollutant in each sampling point of Coimbatore urban

Figure 4.3: The main page of the Web application developed to visualize mobile particulate pollution monitoring values

monitor (the Aerocet 531STM monitor) was combined with a GPS system. The image 4.1 shows the components of mobile monitor prototype with the steel container for carrying it during field sampling on a two-wheeler. The monitor comprised of a battery pack and a single board computer to control the Aerocet 531STM and GPS system to start the sampling recording the location coordinates. To disseminate the mobile sampling data on-line, an interoperable web application was developed. By using HTML, JavaScript and web mapping environment, the location of sampling point and pollution level was interactively visualized.

4.3 Results and Discussion

The spatial variability study carried out during 21 - 23 October 2014 gave an opportunity to compare the spatial variability of particulate pollution during festival days (Diwali celebration) and non-festival days. The current study has recorded $116.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ average PM2.5 (range of $65.8 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to $572.2 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and $454.6 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ average PM10 (range $136 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to $1618 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) for the Diwali day of 22nd October 2014. The values for 21st October 2014 were $101 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ PM2.5 (range $17.8 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to $263.2 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and $472.6 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ PM10 ($27.8 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to $1892.3 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). The values for 23rd October 2014 were PM2.5 $45 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and PM10 $309 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ with range of $35.6 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to $60.9 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $72.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to $931.4 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ respectively. The image 4.2 shows the average values of PM2.5 and PM10 for each sampling point within 1km grid over Coimbatore urban area. As drizzling occurred on 23rd October 2014 with high humidity, most of the samples taken during this date were excluded due to humidity correction. The image 4.2 shows the larger number of grids having high PM2.5 and PM10 during 22nd October 2014 than the other two days of sampling. It is also to be noted that cleansing power of drizzling in reducing the PM2.5 and PM10 over the region as the pollution recorded during 23rd October 2014 shows huge reduction from the pollution level of previous day.

The image shows the web application developed based on the open source code of Meteor application [25]. It is based on D3.js library and based on a drawmap.js file. The customized javascript code used for the mobile monitoring web application is shown

in the section A.3.2. The application takes the mobile monitoring data with sample point coordinates and plots it as a point in the Coimbatore urban map. This point has interactive facility to show the values of particulate pollution readings recorded in each point.

4.4 Conclusion

To extend the objective one of the project, a study was carried out to record the spatial variability of particulate pollution in urban Coimbatore during the festival days. To ease the field deployment and operation, the mobile monitor was customized and equipped with a GPS. For web-based dissemination of the monitor readings a web application was developed. The present trail was to demonstrate the utility of the web application interface, developed as a part of the first objective of the project, for visualization of the data generated from an industrial, but customized particulate monitor.

Chapter 5

Real time particulate pollution modelling for Coimbatore region using WRF-CHEM

5.1 Introduction

Air quality modeling provides superior tools for scientific understanding [26] of the pollution problems and help simulating the situation in view of various regulatory measures to choose best options. It also helps in creating awareness among public on pollution concentration [27] within the pertinent time and space. Scientific and technological development in the past decades has realized the new field of real time air quality forecasting using atmospheric models [26]. The air quality modeling can be broadly grouped into deterministic numerical simulation models and statistical analytical models [28]. The numerical simulation models forecast concentration of air pollutant by simulating the atmospheric condition using meteorological parameters and pollution emission inventory in a region [29]. Weather Research and Forecast with Chemistry (WRF-CHEM) is a widely used weather and air quality-modeling suit. It is an on-line coupled meteorological and atmospheric model [30].

The current chapter addresses the major component of second objective of the project to develop real time air quality modeling web processing service using the sensor observation service (SOS), validate and compare the model output with that from similar other models. This chapter focuses on the development of WRF-CHEM modeling environment for Coimbatore region, its computational requirement in different computer processors and developing an automatic execution script for real time air quality modeling.

5.2 Materials and Methods

The WRF-CHEM model comprised of a WRF Preprocessor System (WPS) and a WRF core module. The WRF proceeds with the model simulation based on the boundary and initial condition over the domain of Coimbatore setup by WPS.

5.2.1 WRF-CHEM model environment set-up

WRF-CHEM model suite is written in FORTRAN and C language, which has parallel execution support and modular functionality, which ease to set-up its environment in different computer processors. WRF-CHEM compilation step consist of testing the

Figure 5.1: The WRF-CHEM model domain used for Coimbatore region

compilers such as GCC, GFORTRAN, GCC+GFORTRAN, and PERL for their compatibility in the computer [31]. This was followed by compilation of NETCDF and MPICH libraries, which gives data write / read and parallel execution functions for WRF-CHEM. The library set-up was followed by configuration of WRF source-code file `configure.wrf` and execution of compilation command. This was followed by WRF pre-processing system (WPS) and emission inventory processor `PREP_CHEM_SRC` compilation. Processor and OS specific difference was considered for above steps in compiling the WRF-CHEM in computers having processors such as Intel i5, Xeon, ARM and Xeon processors of Amazon Web Service (AWS) Elastic compute cloud (EC2).

5.2.2 Model domain and parameter for Coimbatore area

To perform high-resolution modeling of particulate pollution over Coimbatore, a dynamic downscaling of the WRF-CHEM model was done. The domain spreading over the whole of southern India was taken as mother domain with resolution of 27 Km, which was subsequently downscaled by consecutive simulations to have resolution of 9 Km and then 3 Km, which was the lowest domain. The image 5.1 shows diagrammatically the domains used for running the WRF-CHEM over Coimbatore region. Model parameters and input data is elaborated in 8.2.2.

5.2.3 Script for real time running of WRF-CHEM

Typical WRF-CHEM model execution requires WRF preprocessor provided with initial and boundary condition, emission inventory, management of model parameters and dynamic downscaling, altogether comprising of 10-15 individual steps based on the level of downscaling. For real time modeling, script programme would ease and organize the multiple steps involved in execution of models in timely manner without manual interventions. A *Python* based script that can run the WRF [32] was modified to execute the WRF-CHEM in real time.

Table 5.1: Wall clock time taken for various steps of WRF-CHEM executed in different computer processors

Sno	Processor	Compilation	WPS	WRF-CHEM six hour simulation		
				D01	D02	D03
1	Intel Core i5	25 min	<1 min	3 hours	1 hour	6 hours
	3X core			10 min	17 min	55 min
2	Xeon	25 min	<1 min	23 min	46 min	4 hours
	3X core			-	-	51 min
3	Cloud computer-30X cluster	25 min	<1 min	4 min	9 min	58 min
4	ARM 2X cluster	5 hours	-	-	-	-

Figure 5.2: The plot of the common variables of WRF-CHEM output for different domains of dynamic downscaling starting from (left to right) domain 1(27 Km resolution) to domain 3 (3 km resolution)

5.3 Results and Discussion

The WRF-CHEM model was run using different processors such as Intel i5, Xeon, ARM and AWS EC2. The library NETCDF had non-compatibility issues in different versions of Operating Systems (OS), GFORTRAN and GCC compilers. The time taken for model execution for Coimbatore domain varied between the processor. The model execution time taken by various computer processors are given in the table 5.1. The AWS cluster cloud computer significantly reduced the model execution time. Noteworthy raise in compilation time was seen upon using the ARM processor based single board computer (Table 4.1). The image 5.2 shows the plot of various common parameters of WRF-CHEM output carried out by real time execution script over Coimbatore domain. The image 5.3 shows the various steps involved in the WRF-CHEM running with three domain dynamic downscaling. The *Python* script, based on *Python* OS module, provides the facility to call the OS-dependent functionality from inside the script. The section A.4.1 shows the sample code of the WRF-CHEM execution script. The model execution is based on the domain details and various physical and chemical parameters selected for the run. For every simulation, WRF-CHEM parses the variables in the namelist.input file and run simulation as per the description. The file namelist.input describes the various parameters of model run such as details about time of the model execution, source files for boundary and initial condition of model, physical and chemical parameterization of the current model execution etc.

namelist.input and add the appropriate variable based on the domain and stage of WRF-CHEM execution. The script was tested successful error-free execution of simulation without any manual intervention in various processor based WRF-CHEM environment.

5.4 Conclusion

To address the objective two of the project (i.e. developing a real time air quality modeling system), WRF-CHEM based model system was custom-made. A *Python* script was developed for automatic real time execution of the model. The model was successfully configured and run in different computer processor to assess the computational requirement for successful model execution.

Chapter 6

Web visualization of WRF-CHEM model output

6.1 Introduction

Web Processing Service (WPS) provides a set of standards for initiating response and requisites for geo-spatial products in web environment [33]. WRF-CHEM outputs in NETCDF format, non-compatible with web browser environment [34], pose difficulty in visualization as a WPS service. Generally, WRF-CHEM output in web environment was visualized as a set of imageries or plots derived from the NETCDF output [35]. This denies the interactivity and interoperable further usage of WRF-CHEM output in on-line platform. As real time air quality modeling is directed towards improving the common public awareness on issue of air pollution [29], these drawbacks hinder to a great extend wider circulation of the model outputs and their wider usage in online environment.

This chapter addresses these issues related to converting the WRF-CHEM output into JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format, a data format compatible with web browser environment. JSON is an interchangeable data format widely used in web browsers and as a data format in client side programming. The conversion of WRF-CHEM output is also helpful to describe a model with sensor web enablement specification by considering the model as sensor [36]. This gives functionality to describe the model execution in web standards and include the meta-data to give measures that are more interoperable, increases the model output usability and wide circulation. This chapter discusses about the steps in converting the WRF-CHEM output into JSON format and demonstrates the usability of conversion through a web application. A demo web application was developed by consuming the JSON format from WRF-CHEM output in web mapping environment. By demonstrating a web application above the JSON output of WRF-CHEM, this chapter addresses the major component of objective two of the project to develop a non-standard web processing service for real time air quality modeling.

6.2 Materials and Methods

A two-step procedure was followed for interoperable visualization of WRF-CHEM output, conversion into JSON format and interpolation in web map application.

6.2.1 WRF-CHEM output into JSON

The WRF-CHEM output in NETCDF format was serialized by converting into a format, which can be imported into database that can be queried as JSON format. Conventionally

Figure 6.1: Various steps in conversion of WRF-CHEM out put into JSON

the output from WRF does not conform to Climate and Forecast (CF) convention [37], which is a widely adopted standard for NETCDF. For this, the WRF output has to be converted into a CF convention enabled format to extract the normal weather forecast outputs such as temperature, humidity, wind speed, wind direction etc. A NCL language [38] based script was used to convert the NETCDF from WRF-CHEM into CF enabled file format with required variable for visualization.

6.2.2 Web map application for WRF-CHEM output

The serialized WRF-CHEM output was visualized using an open source web application that was used for visualizing data from air pollution monitoring stations in Tokyo [39] earlier. The WRF-CHEM output visualization was enabled by considering the grid output from WRF-CHEM as a monitoring station and importing it into the back-end database of the application. The application is a client side web browser program. It has facility for location specific information retrieval similar to the WPS by clicking on the web map layer interpolated from WRF-CHEM output.

6.3 Results and Discussion

Using NETCDF library [40] of the *Python* programming language, the WRF-CHEM NETCDF output was converted into Comma-Separated Values (CSV) format. The CSV format was chosen for its modularity in importing into database. The image 6.1 shows the steps involved in conversion of the NETCDF into JSON format. The section A.5.1 shows the *Python* programming code for netcdf conversion into JSON. The images from 6.2 to 6.5 show the interface of web application that visualizes WRF-CHEM output. The data from CSV file is imported into postgresQL database and subsequently converted into JSON format while querying for interpolation and smoothing based on map canvas of the Coimbatore urban area. The web application developed is based on Tokyo air program written for visualizing the air pollution observation from different stations in Tokyo [39]. The application is written in node.js for server functionality and D3.JS for data interpolation animation and visualization. It was customized for visualizing WRF-CHEM output by considering the grid centroid coordinates of NETCDF output as monitoring station and importing into the postgresQL backend of the Tokyo air web application. The visualization is carried out by interpolating the coordinates having simulated WRF-CHEM output values for different variables.

Figure 6.2: Web application visualising the WRF-CHEM output for wind direction as base map

Figure 6.3: Web application visualising the WRF-CHEM output variable for PM2.5 as a interpolated layer above the base map

Figure 6.4: Web application visualising the WRF-CHEM output variable for Temperature as a interpolated layer above the base map

Figure 6.5: Web application visualising the WRF-CHEM output variable for wind velocity as a interpolated layer above the base map

6.4 Conclusion

To address the Web processing service for air quality modeling output, a workaround solution was experimented by converting the NETCDF file of WRF-CHEM into interoperable format. The usability of format conversion was demonstrated as a web application providing certain features of Web processing services.

Chapter 7

Anthropogenic emission inventory for particulate pollutants in Coimbatore region

7.1 Introduction

Emission Inventory (EI) is the most important data requirement in air pollution modeling for setting up model's initial and boundary conditions [41]. EI tabulates the amount of different air pollutant species emitted from an area during a particular period of time [42]. As majority of emissions are from anthropogenic activities related to fuel consumption or its auxiliary activities, emission inventories are estimated from potential sources, various activities that consume a particular fuel type and emission factor that is quantity of various pollutants emitted from the fuel consumption [43]. Thus, the basic data requirements for the preparation of emission inventory for an area are i) emission source location, ii) information on activity in those sources and iii) pollutant emission factor. Top-down or bottom-up approaches are followed in EI preparation [42]. In top-down approach, overall fuel consumption is taken as surrogate for emission and using various proxies for emission related activity, the grid level emissions are estimated [43]. In bottom-up approach, various sectors of activity in an area are considered as emission source or pollution emitting activity. Rate of emission from these sectors were estimated separately and then combined together[44].

The current chapter discusses the development of particulate pollution emission inventory for Coimbatore by bottom-up approach considering 2012 as base year. It addresses part of second objective of the project to develop real time particulate pollution modeling using improved emission inventory for the study area.

7.2 Materials and methods

7.3 Study area:

Coimbatore is the second largest and fastest growing city in the state of Tamil Nadu, India. It has population of 3.1 million with population density of 10,052 per km^2 (Census of India 2010). Present corporation limit is around 247 $sq.km^2$. For current attempt of preparing particulate pollutant emission inventory for Coimbatore region, an area of 3000 km^2 covering Coimbatore corporation limit and its surrounding taluks were considered (Fig 7.1).

Figure 7.1: The study area map with extent of area considered for emission inventory calculations

A grid of 1 x 1 Km size was drawn over the Coimbatore region and the grids were used for subsequent emission calculation. The grids spread over 260 villages of the taluks and wards adjacent to the Coimbatore Corporation.

7.3.1 Emission source and activity data

Coimbatore being mainly an industrial urban centre, particulate pollution emission from residential, industrial and transport sector were considered as the three major emission sources. The data for these emission sources were collected from relevant secondary sources such as Census of India 2011, Tamil Nadu Pollution Control Board (TNPCB), Tamil Nadu State Transport Corporation (TNSTC), Regional Transport Offices, Statistical Handbook of Tamil Nadu, Bhuwan Web Map Services and Open street map shape files.

RESIDENTIAL SECTOR Emission source from residential sector were collected from Census of India 2011 data consist of house listing and population enumeration [45]. The village / ward level population enumeration data included total houses per ward / village level and the house listing data consist of percentage of houses using different fuel type for cooking and lighting were used as emission sources. The census data gives proportion of houses using fuels types such as LPG, Kerosene and firewood for cooking activities. For activity data, fuel consumption rate from National Sample survey was used [46]. The data, shown in table 7.1 contains state level per capita consumption for each fuel type. The number of person per house data (from house listing table of the census of India 2011) was used for finding number of members in each house. The emission inventory

Table 7.1: Per capita consumption of various fuel types in Tamil Nadu as per [46] during 2012-2013

S.No	Fuel type	Rural	Urban
1	Firewood and chips (kg)	19.271	3.686
2	Kerosene (liter)	0.613	0.551
3	Electricity Kwh	17.016	36.426
4	LPG (kg)	0.948	2.17
5	Coal/charcoal (kg)	0.002	0.0

Figure 7.2: Road network in Coimbatore region

grid was chosen based on build-up land use in the particular grid. High resolutions satellite imageries from Web Mapping Services such as Google map were used for designating the grid as barren land or build up land. Grids containing only the built-up structures were used for further emission inventory calculation.

TRANSPORT SECTOR Emission sources from road transport are calculated by considering the road network as source of emission. Open street map data containing road network layer within Coimbatore region were used. The map 7.2 shows the categorized road network of Coimbatore region. On-road vehicle activity were calculated using data from Statistical handbook of Tamil Nadu 2014[47], which tabulates the district level vehicular population. Vehicular Kilometer Travel (VKT) data for a typical urban India [44] were used. The table 7.2 shows the vehicular population, VKT and Emission Factor per vehicle type. To distribute the vehicular emission levels into the spatial format of road network, the road network data of Coimbatore region was categorized into five types such as trunk, primary, secondary, tertiary and other roads, in which the proportion of the vehicular movement at a given time was assumed from the importance of the particular road type in connectivity.

In Coimbatore, diesel based buses are major public transportation means. These are

Table 7.2: Vehicular population in Coimbatore district during 2012-2013

Type	No. of Vehicles[47]	PM 10 EF(g/km)[48]	VKT [44]
Two wheelers	1423384	0.049	75
Four wheelers	244661	0.19	90
Goods vehicle	105414	1.965	150
Autorickshaw	11041	0.347	150
Bus	3766	1.075	210

Figure 7.3: Coimbatore public transport bus route network and total schedule trips crossing each 1Km grids

mainly operated by TNSSTC and small private operators. TNSSTC - Coimbatore controls a fleet of 3267 and 1724 unique routes spreading over adjoining districts such as Nilgiris and Erode. A total of 467 unique bus routes shuttling within the emission inventory grid were considered for the present study. Daily trip-sheets of the buses were collected from TNSSTC and in the case of private players from the Regional transport Offices. Using these data a route network of each bus routes were developed by following the bus stops, start and ends point of each route. By combining the schedule and number of trips per day for each bus route an accurate VKT was developed for public transport systems in Coimbatore along with source of emission as bus route lines and its intersection in emission grid. The image 7.3 shows the Public transport bus route network and total number of schedule trips crossing each grids per day in emission inventory grid of Coimbatore.

For estimation of the road dust emission, factors such as number of rain/wet days and the road quality were considered. During 2012, 28 days were wet days in Coimbatore. The brims of the total roads in the region are unpaved (100%). Other important variables such as average silt loading and average weighted vehicle run over the road were also considered. The average silt load taken was 0.531 gm^{-2} and average weight 1.41 tons as per a surrogate urban Indian condition (an estimated values in Delhi conditions [44]).

INDUSTRIAL SECTOR Being second largest industrial hub of Tamil Nadu, Coimbatore hosts several categories of air pollutant causative industries such as Cement, foundries,

Table 7.3: Year wise fuel consumption in Coimbatore(kL/year)(taken from [49] tables 3-6)

Year	Petrol		Diesel		
	Transport	Industries	Transport	Industries	Commercial
2007-2008	61374	15344	117058.9	33445.4	16722.7
2008-2009	68558	17139	137474.4	39278.4	19639.2
2009-2010	58402	14601	105676.2	30193.2	15096.6
2010-2011	62802	15700	121689.4	34768.4	17384.2

Table 7.4: Emission factor for each sector and fuel type(from [44] table 4)

Sector	Pollutant	Unit	CNG/NG	LPG	Wood	Diesel	Coal /Coke	Kerosene	FO	Cow dung
Industries	PM10 ^a	g unit ⁻¹	0	-	-	0.0009	-	-	-	-
	PM2.5 ^b	g kg ⁻¹	0.34	0.31	-	0.97	1.36	0.34	0.65	-
Residential	PM10 ^c	g kg ⁻¹	-	2.1	15.3	-	20.0	1.95d	-	-
	PM2.5 ^b	g kg ⁻¹	-	0.33	1.5	-	12.2	1.9d	-	5.04

brick kilns and stone crushers. Data on industries covering the pollution category of the industry, address and annual production were obtained from TNPCB. The Coimbatore region, taken for emission inventory preparation, hosts 2 large-scale cement-manufacturing units with annual production of 438000-1200000 Ton/year. It also hosts around 722 foundry units using coal and furnace oil as their primary source of energy. The activity data for these industries were estimated from its annual production and consumption of fuel required for per tonne of product. Genset usages were also considered for emission calculation. For this, industries, institutions, commercial complexes were located and average fuel consumption and activity per day was included in calculation. The table 7.3 shows year wise fuel consumption in Coimbatore urban area.

7.3.2 Emission factors, calculation and spatial allocation

Emission Factor (EF) is a major determinant of pollutant concentration and accuracy of emission inventory. Estimation of Emission factor, which involves estimating quantity of particulate pollutant from a typical activity of a sector using specific fuel type calculation, is a complex process. Hence, generally values for emission factor are taken from secondary sources. In the case of the present study we depended on sector specific scenario and mission based studies by CPCB (study on Air quality monitoring, EI and source apportionment study for Indian cities - 2010) [48] and a study on New Delhi [50]. The values reproduced in table 7.4 shows various fuel specific emission factors used in the current study.

In the current study, emission estimation is carried out by bottom-up approach in which major activity and source contribution towards particulate pollution is considered. The vehicular emission is calculated by formula 7.1.

$$E_t = \sum (Veh_l * D_l) * EF_{l,km} \quad (7.1)$$

where E_t = total emission of the compounds; Veh_l = number of vehicles of each type; D_l = distance travelled in a year per different vehicle type, derived from VKT per day; $EF_{l,km}$ = emission of compound, vehicle type per driven kilometer.

The total emission from vehicular population is spatially allocated to each grid by assumed volume proportion passing over different road category at a given time [51]. The equation 7.2 was used to allocate the total emission from vehicular population to each grid

$$E = \left(\frac{LT_i}{\sum LT_i} * 0.38 + \frac{LP_i}{\sum LP_i} * 0.28 + \frac{LS_i}{\sum LS_i} * 0.15 + \frac{LT_e_i}{\sum LT_e_i} * 0.13 + \frac{LR_i}{\sum LR_i} * 0.06 \right) * C \quad (7.2)$$

Where, E_i = total emission in i th grid, LT_i = total length of the trunk roads in the i th grid, LP_i = total length of the primary roads in the i th grid, LS_i = total length of the secondary roads in the i th grid, LT_e_i = total length of the tertiary roads in the i th grid, LR_i = total length of the other roads in the i th grid and C = total vehicular emission as per equation 7.1.

Emission from unpaved roads are calculated using the formula 7.3.

$$E = \left[\left(\frac{K(S/12)^{0.8}(W/3)^{0.4}}{(M/0.2)^{0.3}} \right) * (N - P) / N \right] \quad (7.3)$$

Where E = particulate EF (g VKT⁻¹), sL = road surface silt loading (g m²), S = surface material silt content, P = number of wet days with at least 0.254 mm (0.01 in) of precipitation for the averaging period (365 days), K = particle size multiplier for particle size range (g VKT⁻¹), W = mean vehicle weight (tons), M = surface material moisture content (%).

The total emission is calculated using the formula 7.4 based on works such as [44, 50, 52, 53]. Total emission from all the sector is calculated as follows,

$$TE = \sum_a \sum_b FU_{a,b} \left[\sum_c EF_{a,b,c} U_{a,b,c} \right] \quad (7.4)$$

where a = sectors for which EI was prepared, b = fuel type, and c = technology, TE is total emission, FU is fuel utilization, EF is emission factor for each fuel type, U is the fraction of fuel under a sector (transport, road, residential etc) with specific re-mediation technology in place to contain pollution emission. As there is no emission remediation technology considered in the present situation the respective factor for this aspect is taken as 1.

Grid level spatial allocation of emission inventory is carried out by using geospatial tools of the *Python* [54] programming language and its libraries such as *Numpy*, *Pandas*, *Fiona*, *Geopandas* and *Shapely*. The image 7.4 shows the process involved in the case of residential sector emission inventory computation. The ward / village boundary map of Coimbatore region was conjoined with respective data from census of India 2011. This was then overlaid on the 1x1 Km grid and was selected to join with each grid space. On this grid level data, the emission inventory calculations were carried out by joining respective EF and fuel consumption. The appendix A.6.1 provides the *Python* codes used to carry out these processes.

The processes involved in emission inventory calculation for transport sector was shown in the image 7.5. Total emission from transport sector was calculated using the formula 7.1 and the grid level extraction of this emission was carried out using the formula 7.2 on the spatial data comprised of different road category within each grid. Grid level road categories were developed by overlaying the grid shape files on road network shape files and extracting the intersecting road features within each grid extent. Fast spatial indexer such as Rtree index was used to carry out this step to optimize computation requirements.

Figure 7.4: Various steps involved in residential sector emission inventory calculation

Figure 7.5: Various steps involved in Transport sector emission inventory calculation

For public transport system emission inventory, trip-sheets of the bus routes, which give details about the route and stops in the route, were used. The stops were geocoded and this coordinates were interconnected to form bus route line features, which was corrected by intersecting the derived route line features above the road network. The intersecting sections in the route, overlaid upon by the grid polygon, were extracted to calculate the emission inventory. This section A.6.2 shows *Python* codes used to derive the transport sector based particulate emission inventory.

The industrial sector emission inventory calculation process is shown in the figure 7.6. The emission inventory was prepared at grid level by converting the address data into geocodes by reverse geocoding and overlaying the grid on point features of industrial location. The grids containing the industrial feature were then subjected to the emission inventory calculation. Appendix show the *Python* codes used to derive the industrial sector emission inventory A.6.3.

The sector wise emission inventory was then used to estimate the total emission for particulate matter PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ in the study area. Then the grid based emission inventory was plotted by Natural Breaks Map Classification. The code used for plotting grid level emission inventory was show in appendix A.6.4.

7.4 Results and Discussion

7.4.1 Anthropogenic PM_{2.5} emission from different sectors of Coimbatore region

The spatial distribution of total PM_{2.5} emission from different sectors of Coimbatore region for the year 2012 is depicted in the image 7.7. The total estimated emission of PM_{2.5} from different sources together was found to be 12125.7 Ton/year in 2012. Of this, the contribution from residential sector, transport sector, windblown dust and industrial source were 169.5 Ton/year, 4488.6 Ton/year, 918.1 Ton/year and 6549.4 Ton/year respectively. The relative contribution of residential sector was 1.4 %, transport sector 37.0 %, windblown dust 7.6% and industrial sector 54.0%, as depicted in the images from 7.8 to 7.11.

It is observed from image 7.7 that high PM_{2.5} emission in the range of 53.2 to 1305.3 Ton/year are found from the South western, eastern and some of north eastern part of Coimbatore region. It was found that southern part of Coimbatore is one of the most polluted regions where in the industrial sector contributes most to the emission since this region host two large cement-manufacturing units and stone crushers.

7.4.2 Anthropogenic PM₁₀ emission from different sectors of Coimbatore region

Spatial distribution of total PM₁₀ emission from different sectors of Coimbatore region for the year 2012 is depicted in the image 7.12. The total estimated emission of PM₁₀ from different sources together is estimated to be around 13112.9 Ton/year in 2012. Of this, the contributions from residential sector, transport sector, windblown dust and Industrial source were 1608.1 Ton/year, 1030.4 Ton/year, 3842.5 Ton/year and 6631.7 Ton/year respectively. The relative contribution of residential sector was 12.3 %, transport sector 7.9 %, windblown dust 29.3% and industrial sector 50.6 %, as depicted in the images 7.13 to 7.16. It is observed from the image 7.12 that high PM₁₀ emissions (44.7 to 1073.8 Ton/year) are emitted from the west central part of Coimbatore region.

Figure 7.6: Various steps involved in Industrial sector emission inventory calculation

Figure 7.7: Total PM_{2.5} emission from Coimbatore region

Figure 7.8: PM_{2.5} emission from residential sector of Coimbatore region

Figure 7.9: PM2.5 emission from Transport sector of Coimbatore region

Figure 7.10: PM2.5 emission from wind blown dust in Coimbatore region

Figure 7.11: PM2.5 emission from Industrial sector in Coimbatore region

Figure 7.12: Total PM10 emission from Coimbatore region
PM10 Emissions from Residential Sector in Coimbatore region(1 km resolution)

Figure 7.13: PM10 emission from residential sector in Coimbatore region

Figure 7.14: PM10 emission from Transport sector in Coimbatore region

Figure 7.15: PM10 emission from wind blown dust in Coimbatore region

Figure 7.16: PM10 emission from Industrial sector in Coimbatore region

The PM10 distribution in rest of the region is similar to PM2.5 emission. It has been found large cluster of brick kiln industries are located in west central part of the Coimbatore region.

7.5 Conclusion

As a measure to enhance the simulation result for real time particulate pollution modeling, emission inventory for PM2.5 and PM10 for Coimbatore region was developed in this work. It has been found that the total emission of PM10 and PM2.5 is 12125.7 Ton/year and 13112.9 Ton/year respectively in the region during 2012. The emission from Industrial sector is found to be the major contributor in particulate pollution. Stringent regulatory measures for the un-organized sectors such as Brick kiln industries and stone crushers would be required to better the air quality in region.

Chapter 8

Inter comparison of emission inventories and evaluation of WRF-CHEM output for Coimbatore domain

8.1 Introduction

Emission Inventories (EIs) provide basic data input for air quality modelling [44]. There are several EIs custom made for specific objective of the studies such as to simulate the climate change impact and meso-scale chemistry transport. The localized EIs are developed to address the local air quality modelling issues and it is mostly developed at sectoral level of the area with extent of urban or district level. To input this emission inventory into WRF- CHEM modelling system, it needs to be converted into the WRF-CHEM importable format and grid pattern of the model system. For this, integrating with global level EIs is an option. EDGAR HTAP v2 EI [55] is a most updated global level EI for variables such as PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀. This facilitates the utilization of localized emission inventory for WRF -CHEM by integrating with it.

Model evaluation provides measure of agreement between predicted values and observed values [56]. This is used for finding the effectiveness of air quality simulation and its data usability for other purposes. This chapter address the objective 2 component to compare the emission inventory created by integrating the local level emission inventory on global level. It also aims to evaluate the simulation output of WRF-CHEM over Coimbatore region.

8.2 Materials and methods

8.2.1 Emission inventory (EI) Inter comparison

The inter comparisons of EIs were carried out by integrating Coimbatore (CBE) EI for PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ on EDGAR HTAP EI v2 [57]. The image 8.1 shows the various steps involved in generating the emission inventories for comparison. The python programming language handler for NETCDF4 format was used to extract the array from EDGAR HTAP file. The emission inventory grid for HTAP and EDGAR was summed based on the grid super imposing after cumulative up-scaling of the CBE EI from 1 km into 10 km. The section A.7.1 shows the various programming steps followed for integrating the CBE emission inventory on EDGAR EI. The inter comparison of before and after integration

Figure 8.1: Steps involved in integrating the Coimbatore local emission inventory over EDGAR HTAP global inventory

was carried out for PM10 and PM2.5 pollutant range, average and sum of values in each domain used for the WRF-CHEM simulation. The program Anthro_emiss was used to plot the emission inventory for whole globe into the simulation domain for Coimbatore and data format suitable of WRF-CHEM.

8.2.2 WRF-CHEM output evaluation

WRF-CHEM evaluation for Coimbatore domain was carried out by comparing the simulation output with ground based in-situ observations. The weather monitoring parameters from Coimbatore air port taken from Weather Underground [58] web site was used for comparing meteorological parameters such as temperature and humidity. The data from Aerocet 531STM was used for comparing the particulate matters PM2.5 and PM10 from WRF-CHEM simulations. Various statistical measures were used to find the extent of agreement between observation and WRF-CHEM model predictions.

For the model's initial and boundary conditions, the global forecasting system data from National Centre for Environmental Prediction (NCEP) final analysis was used; the data has spatial resolution of 1 degree and temporal resolution of six hours. This data is suitable for real time modeling since it is updated four times daily at six-hour intervals. For anthropogenic emissions, RETRO/EDGAR Global anthropogenic emissions were used after processing it with PREP_CHEM_SRC [59]. Physical parameterization schemes such as microphysics [60], Noah Land Surface Model [61], the YSU PBL scheme [62], KainFritsch cumulus parameterization scheme [63] and Rapid Radiative Transfer Model (RRTM) long wave radiation scheme [64] were used for the model. Model parameterization studies over New Delhi had shown that the WRF performs better with these physical parametrizations. Goddard Global Ozone Chemistry Aerosol Radiation and Transport (GOCART) aerosol model was selected for aerosol simulation [65]. The R statistical programming language and Open-air [66] package was used for applying the statistical evaluation measures. The section A.7.2 shows the programming code samples used for model output validation.

8.3 Results and Discussions

8.3.1 Emission inventory (EI) inter-comparison

The image 8.2 shows the plots of Coimbatore emission inventory overlaid on EDGAR HTAP emission inventory. The table 8.1 shows the range, mean and sum values of PM2.5 and PM10 values in emission inventories over the domain-1 of the WRF-CHEM simulation for Coimbatore.

Figure 8.2: Plot of EDGAR HTAP EI (A) and Coimbatore EI (B) for PM2.5 and PM10

Table 8.1: PM2.5 and PM10 from values from EDGAR HTAP EI and Coimbatore EI for WRF-CHEM model domain 01

		Domains	Domain Resolution	Domain EI resolution	Emission range $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}^{-1}$	Emission total $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}^{-1}$	Emission mean $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}^{-1}$
EDGAR HTAP	PM2.5	Domain 1	27 km	10KM	0-1.6	263.18	0.03
		Domain 2	9 km	10KM	0-0.9	291.6	0.05
		Domain 3	3 km	10KM	0.02-0.45	766.6	0.07
	PM10	Domain 1	27 km	10KM	0-3.8	352.01	0.04
		Domain 2	9 km	10KM	0-2.19	362.1	0.06
		Domain 3	3 km	10KM	0.02-0.94	880.0	0.08
CBE EI	PM2.5	Domain 1	27 km	1 KM	0-26.52	326.9	0.04
		Domain 2	9 km	1 KM	0-47.42	863.62	0.15
		Domain 3	3 km	1 KM	0.02-54.2	5931.9	0.58
	PM10	Domain 1	27 km	1 KM	0-26.53	415.7	0.05
		Domain 2	9 km	1 KM	0-47.43	934.1	0.17
		Domain 3	3 km	1 KM	0.02-54.21	6045.4	0.59

8.3.2 WRF-CHEM output evaluation

The model evaluation statistical measures [67, 68] were used for validating WRF-CHEM output against in-situ observations. The measures such as Fraction of predictions within a factor or two (*FAC2*), Mean Bias (*MB*), Mean Gross Error (*MGE*), Normalised Mean Bias (*NMB*), Normalised Mean Gross Error (*NMGE*), Root Mean Squared Error (*RMSE*), Correlation Coefficient (*r*), Coefficient of Efficiency (*COE*). The formula for finding these statistical measures are

$$FAC2 = 0.5 \leq \frac{M_i}{O_i} \leq 2.0 \quad (8.1)$$

$$MB = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^N M_i - O_i \quad (8.2)$$

$$MGE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^N |M_i - O_i| \quad (8.3)$$

$$NMB = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n M_i - O_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n O_i} \quad (8.4)$$

$$NMGE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |M_i - O_i|}{\sum_{i=1}^n O_i} \quad (8.5)$$

$$RMSE = \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (M_i - O_i)^2}{n} \right)^{1/2} \quad (8.6)$$

$$r = \frac{1}{(n-1)} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{M_i - \bar{M}}{\sigma_M} \right) \left(\frac{O_i - \bar{O}}{\sigma_O} \right) \quad (8.7)$$

$$COE = 1.0 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |M_i - O_i|}{\sum_{i=1}^n |O_i - \bar{O}|} \quad (8.8)$$

$$IOA = \begin{cases} 1.0 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |M_i - O_i|}{c \sum_{i=1}^n |O_i - \bar{O}|}, \text{ when} \\ \sum_{i=1}^n |M_i - O_i| \leq c \sum_{i=1}^n |O_i - \bar{O}| \\ \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |O_i - \bar{O}|}{\sum_{i=1}^n |M_i - O_i|} - 1.0, \text{ when} \\ \sum_{i=1}^n |M_i - O_i| > c \sum_{i=1}^n |O_i - \bar{O}| \end{cases} \quad (8.9)$$

where M_i is the model predictions, O_i is the observations, \bar{M} , \bar{O} are mean for model prediction and observation variables respectively. The table 8.2 shows the evaluation

Table 8.2: Evaluation statistics for WRF-CHEM simulation for Coimbatore and in situ observation during 14 January 2015 to 15 January 2015

S.No	Variables	n	FAC2	MB	MGEN	NMB	NMGE	RMSE	r	COE
1	Temperature	34	1.0	-3.3	4.7	-0.14	0.21	5.71	0.031	-0.56
2	Relative Humidity	34	0.85	16.2	23.4	0.25	0.37	27.44	-0.19	-0.66
3	PM2.5	14	0.0	-88.7	88.7	-0.98	0.98	93.76	-0.11	-2.35
4	PM10	14	0.0	-216.8	216.8	-0.99	0.99	235.31	0.09	-1.96

statistics for the model simulation over Coimbatore during 14 January 2015 to 15 January 2015. From the table it could be observed that none of the variables simulated by WRF-CHEM are in close values with the observed variables. This would indicate need of refined parameterization for WRF-CHEM simulation over Coimbatore domain. It warrants further elaborate sensitivity study focusing on micro physics and various gas phase mechanisms options similar to the study carried out by [69].

8.3.3 Conclusion

As a measure to input the Coimbatore Emission inventory for WRF-CHEM simulation, an attempt was made to integrate the Coimbatore emission inventory with Global emission inventory EDGAR HTAP. The model evaluation study carried out for the output from WRF-CHEM simulation over Coimbatore necessitate further study and refinement to resolve the various microphysics and gas phase mechanisms option suitable for the domain.

Chapter 9

Mobile application for location specific particulate pollution information

9.1 Introduction

Location relevance improves the usability of real time information [70]. Currently public, being increasingly adept with mobile devices, are using these devices as a primary means of information access. The information access at users' current location through mobile devices can open up a large pool of applications in terms of better advisory and awareness creation. For integrated environmental management in particulate air pollution domain, it will help in providing important health advisories or warnings specific to users' location using simple means of communication such as geo-tagged Short Message Services (SMS). This chapter addresses the third and final objective of the project to develop a Geo-SMS based android application to disseminate the modeling result. This objective was achieved by developing a client side android application for the mobile phones and a server side K dimensional tree (KD-tree) [71] algorithm based script to parse the model output with response to the geotagged SMS query.

9.2 Materials and Methods

The mobile application for location specific particulate pollution information comprised of a server side program and client side Android application.

9.2.1 Client side Android application

The client side program comprised of an Android application, which can be used widely with available smart phones. The Android application will be facilitated by map view of the current location and an interface to query the particulate pollution in the area that can be sent as SMS to the server to get the response.

9.2.2 Server side program

The server side program comprised of KD-tree geo-spatial algorithm, which respond to the location specific queries from client side application in Geo-tagged SMS format. The server side program also included an SMS gateway that receives the users' queries

Figure 9.1: Off-line map view of the client side android application

Figure 9.2: On touch GeoSMS send activity of the client side android application

Figure 9.3: Components and processes in server side program

as SMS and responds with an output of geo-spatial algorithm with location relevant particulate pollution information.

9.3 Results and Discussion

9.3.1 Client side Android application

The android application comprised of an offline map with touch response on the screen. The user can locate their position by either GPS based localization or using landmark localization. When the location is positioned, the user can touch on the map screen, which prompt the latitude and longitude of the position to be send as a Geo SMS to the server side SMS gateway. The Geo SMS specification format is based on Matthew Kwan [72] and it is as follows.

What is the air quality here?(76.123158, 11.596485), u = 5

The android code of the developed application is based on an offline map app [73]. The images 9.1 and 9.2 shows the various functionality of the android application. The Android code comprised of a main activity, which shows the map with helper functions like tile manager and tile provider. The main activity is further assisted by a map view and map location listener functions. These two functions enable GPS localization and to send an SMS in GeoSMS specification carrying the coordinates of the current position clicked on the map. The section A.8.1 shows the map-view activity instance sample code of the Android application, which over see the on touch sending of the location coordinates as Geo SMS.

9.3.2 Server side program

For server side program, KD-tree algorithm based program was used to respond location specific queries. The image shows the components involved in server side program 9.3. KDtree algorithm based on KD-tree data structure was used. The algorithm spatially partitions the data for better searching in K - Dimensional space. It is best suitable for nearest neighbor search. The KD-tree algorithm application on NETCDF format was used to organize the client side program [74]. The GAMMU SMS [75] gateway was used as SMS server, which is compiled in Beagle bone black single board computer and assigned as server. The section A.8.2 shows the sample code of server side program script. The GAMMU was configured to automatic response to SMS query, which carry specific keyword to run the KD-tree algorithm.

9.4 Conclusion

Combining the server side program and client side android application, Geo-SMS based android application was developed to disseminate the model results on location specific queries.

Bibliography

- [1] Amanda L Northcross, Rufus J Edwards, Michael A Johnson, Zhong-Min Wang, Kunning Zhu, Tracy Allen, and Kirk R Smith. A low-cost particle counter as a realtime fine-particle mass monitor. *Environmental Science: Processes & Impacts*, 15(2):433–439, 2013.
- [2] DM Holstius, A Pillarisetti, KR Smith, and E Seto. Field calibrations of a low-cost aerosol sensor at a regulatory monitoring site in California. *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques*, 7(4):1121–1131, 2014.
- [3] Meiling Gao, Junji Cao, and Edmund Seto. A distributed network of low-cost continuous reading sensors to measure spatiotemporal variations of PM_{2.5} in Xi’an, China. *Environmental Pollution*, 199:56–65, 2015.
- [4] Team AQE. Air Quality Egg. <http://airqualityegg.wikispaces.com/AirQualityEgg>, 2012. (Visited on 03/23/2015).
- [5] YR Kolupula, MA Aceves-Fernandez, GR Jones, AG Deakin, and JW Spencer. Airborne particle monitoring with urban closed-circuit television camera networks and a chromatic technique. *Measurement Science and Technology*, 21(11):115204, 2010.
- [6] N Ramanathan, M Lukac, T Ahmed, A Kar, PS Praveen, T Honles, I Leong, IH Rehman, JJ Schauer, and V Ramanathan. A cellphone based system for large-scale monitoring of black carbon. *Atmospheric Environment*, 45(26):4481–4487, 2011.
- [7]
- [8] Justin Arling, Kyle O’Connor, and Michael Mercieca. Air quality sensor network for Philadelphia. http://wireless.ece.drexel.edu/air_quality/project%20files/Engineering%20Manual.pdf, 2011.
- [9] A Tittarelli, A Borgini, M Bertoldi, E De Saeger, A Ruprecht, R Stefanoni, G Tagliabue, P Contiero, and P Crosignani. Estimation of particle mass concentration in ambient air using a particle counter. *Atmospheric Environment*, 42(36):8543–8548, 2008.
- [10] Ji Yi Lee, Hye Jung Shin, Soo Ya Bae, Yong Pyo Kim, and Chang-Hee Kang. Seasonal variation of particle size distributions of PAHs at Seoul, Korea. *Air Quality, Atmosphere & Health*, 1(1):57–68, 2008.
- [11] Jonas Eberle, Siegfried Clausnitzer, Christian Hüttich, and Christiane Schullius. Multi-source data processing middleware for land monitoring within a web-based spatial data infrastructure for Siberia. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 2(3):553–576, 2013.

- [12] Zhong Zheng, Nengcheng Chen, Pengfei Li, and Wei Wang. Integration of hydrological observations into a spatial data infrastructure under a sensor web environment. *International Journal of Digital Earth*, 6(sup2):22–40, 2013.
- [13] M Cannata, M Molinari, and M Pozzoni. Istsos sensor observation management system: A real case application of hydro-meteorological data for flood protection. In *Proceedings of International Workshop of The Role of Geomatics in hydrogeological Risk, Padua, Italy*, pages 27–28, 2013.
- [14] Bernd Resch, Carlo Ratti, Christine Outram, Rex Britter, and Xiaoji Chen. *Standardised geo-sensor webs for integrated urban air quality monitoring*. INTECH Open Access Publisher, 2011.
- [15] Project EO2 heaven. EO2 heaven: Mitigating environmental health risks. <http://www.eo2heaven.org/sites/default/files/content-files/documents/eo2heavenbook.pdf>, 2011. (Visited on 03/21/2015).
- [16] J Lelieveld, C Barlas, D Giannadaki, and A Pozzer. Model calculated global, regional and megacity premature mortality due to air pollution. *Atmos. Chem. Phys*, 13: 7023–7037, 2013.
- [17] Milind Kandlikar and Gurumurthy Ramachandran. The causes and consequences of particulate air pollution in urban india: a synthesis of the science. *Annual Review of Energy and the Environment*, 25(1):629–684, 2000.
- [18] Ali Kaushar, Dilip Chate, Gufran Beig, Reka Srinivas, Neha Parkhi, Trupti Satpute, Saroj Sahu, Sachin Ghude, Santosh Kulkarni, Divya Surendran, et al. Spatio-temporal variation and deposition of fine and coarse particles during the commonwealth games in Delhi. *Aerosol Air Qual. Res*, 13:748–755, 2013.
- [19] Karl Aberer, Saket Sathe, Dipanjan Chakraborty, Alcherio Martinoli, Guillermo Barrenetxea, Boi Faltings, and Lothar Thiele. Opensense: open community driven sensing of environment. In *Proceedings of the ACM SIGSPATIAL International Workshop on GeoStreaming*, pages 39–42. ACM, 2010.
- [20] EPA US. Roadmap for next generation air monitoring. <http://www2.epa.gov/air-research/roadmap-next-generation-air-monitoring>, 2012. (Visited on 03/21/2015).
- [21] AQICN. Dylos air particle counter experimentation, part 1. <http://aqicn.org/faq/2013-09-08/dylos-air-particule-counter-experimentation-part-1/>, 2012. (Visited on 03/21/2015).
- [22] Mpfeil. Mpfeil/qualityschu GitHub. <https://github.com/mpfeil/qualitySCHU>, 2012. (Visited on 03/21/2015).
- [23] Naresh Kumar and Andrew D Foster. Air quality interventions and spatial dynamics of air pollution in delhi and its surroundings. *International journal of environment and waste management*, 4(1):85–111, 2009.
- [24] Ario Alberto Ruprecht, Giovanni Invernizzi, Bertrand Dautzenberg, Luke Clancy, Josè Precioso, Cinzia De Marco, Roberto Boffi, Roberto Mazza, Maria Josè Lopez, and Hanns Moshhammer. Mass calibration and relative humidity compensation requirements for optical portable particulate matter monitors: the IMPASHS (Impact

- of smoke-free policies in EU Member States) WP2 preliminary results. *Epidemiology*, 22(1):S206, 2011.
- [25] Meteors. Wheel/meteors github. <https://github.com/1wheel/meteors>, 2012. (Visited on 03/28/2015).
- [26] Yang Zhang, Marc Bocquet, Vivien Mallet, Christian Seigneur, and Alexander Baklanov. Real-time air quality forecasting, part I: History, techniques, and current status. *Atmospheric Environment*, 60:632–655, 2012.
- [27] Mordechai E Haklay. Public access to environmental information: past, present and future. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 27(2):163–180, 2003.
- [28] Despina Deligiorgi and Kostas Philippopoulos. *Spatial interpolation methodologies in urban air pollution modeling: application for the greater area of metropolitan Athens, Greece*. INTECH Open Access Publisher, 2011.
- [29] Yang Zhang, Marc Bocquet, Vivien Mallet, Christian Seigneur, and Alexander Baklanov. Real-time air quality forecasting, part II: State of the science, current research needs, and future prospects. *Atmospheric Environment*, 60:656–676, 2012.
- [30] Georg A Grell, Steven E Peckham, Rainer Schmitz, Stuart A McKeen, Gregory Frost, William C Skamarock, and Brian Eder. Fully coupled online chemistry within the WRF model. *Atmospheric Environment*, 39(37):6957–6975, 2005.
- [31] WRF-ARW. Online tutorial. <http://www2.mmm.ucar.edu/wrf/OnLineTutorial/index.php>, 2012. (Visited on 03/24/2015).
- [32] RL John. johnrobertlawson/lazywrf GitHub. <https://github.com/johnrobertlawson/lazyWRF>, 2012. (Visited on 03/24/2015).
- [33] Open Geospatial Consortium Inc. Opengis web processing service (WPS) specification. http://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=24151. (Visited on 03/02/2015).
- [34] Scott Ganson and JT Johnson. Challenges of displaying dynamic weather content in interactive mapping solutions. <https://ams.confex.com/ams/pdfpapers/133545.pdf>. (Visited on 03/02/2015).
- [35] M Laka-Iñurrategi, I Alberdi, K Alonso, and M Quartulli. Cloud based N-dimensional weather forecast visualization tool with image analysis capabilities. *ISPRS-International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, 1(2):133–137, 2013.
- [36] Kym Watson and Hylke van der Schaaf. Describing models on the web using OGC standards. www.mssanz.org.au/modsim2013, 2013.
- [37] Brian Eaton, Jonathan Gregory, Bob Drach, Karl Taylor, Steve Hankin, John Caron, Rich Signell, Phil Bentley, Greg Rappa, Heinke Höck, et al. NetCDF Climate and Forecast (CF) metadata conventions. <http://cfconventions.org/>, 2003.
- [38] Foehn. wrfout_to_cf.ncl - overview. http://foehn.colorado.edu/wrfout_to_cf/. (Visited on 03/02/2015).
- [39] Beccario Cameron. cambecc/air GitHub. <https://github.com/cambecc/air>, 2012. (Visited on 03/26/2015).

- [40] Unidata. Unidata/netcdf4-python GitHub. <https://github.com/Unidata/netcdf4-python>, 2012. (Visited on 03/26/2015).
- [41] Alice B Gilliland, Christian Hogrefe, Robert W Pinder, James M Godowitch, Kristen L Foley, and ST Rao. Dynamic evaluation of regional air quality models: Assessing changes in O₃ stemming from changes in emissions and meteorology. *Atmospheric Environment*, 42(20):5110–5123, 2008.
- [42] Manju Mohan, Shweta Bhati, Preeti Gunwani, and Pallavi Marappu. *Air Quality - New Perspective*, chapter Emission Inventory of Air Pollutants and Trend Analysis Based on Various Regulatory Measures Over Megacity Delhi. INTECH Open Access Publisher, Croatia, 2004.
- [43] Ye Huang, Huizhong Shen, Han Chen, Rong Wang, Yanyan Zhang, Shu Su, Yuanchen Chen, Nan Lin, Shaojie Zhuo, Qirui Zhong, et al. Quantification of global primary emissions of PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, and TSP from combustion and industrial process sources. *Environmental science & technology*, 48(23):13834–13843, 2014.
- [44] Saroj Kumar Sahu, Gufran Beig, and Neha S Parkhi. Emissions inventory of anthropogenic pm 2.5 and pm 10 in Delhi during commonwealth games 2010. *Atmospheric Environment*, 45(34):6180–6190, 2011.
- [45] COI. Census of India Website : Office of the Registrar General & Census Commissioner, India. <http://censusindia.gov.in/>, 2012. (Visited on 03/19/2015).
- [46] NSSO. House hold consumption of various goods and services in India, 2011-2012, NSS 68th round. http://mospi.nic.in/mospi_new/upload/Report_no558_rou68_30june14.pdf, 2014. (Visited on 03/19/2015).
- [47] DES. Statistical hand book of Tamil Nadu- 2014. <http://www.tn.gov.in/deptst/>, 2012. (Visited on 03/19/2015).
- [48] CPCB. Air quality monitoring, EI and source apportionment study for Indian cities national summary report. <http://moef.nic.in/downloads/public-information/Rpt-air-monitoring-17-01-2011.pdf>, 2010. (Visited on 03/20/2015).
- [49] MNRE. Development of Coimbatore solar city final master plan. http://mnre.gov.in/file-manager/UserFiles/Coimbatore_solar_city_master_plan.pdf, August 2012. (Visited on 03/20/2015).
- [50] SK Sahu, G Beig, and C Sharma. Decadal growth of black carbon emissions in India. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 35(2), 2008.
- [51] P Goyal and Neeru Jaiswal. Vehicular emissions intervention in Delhi, India. http://www.indianjournals.com/glogift2k6/glogift2k6-1-1/theme_1/Article%202.htm, 2012. (Visited on 03/20/2015).
- [52] Zbigniew Klimont, Janusz Cofala, Imrich Bertok, Markus Amann, Chris Heyes, and F Gyarmas. Modelling particulate emissions in Europe: A framework to estimate reduction potential and control costs. *International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis*, 2002.
- [53] Tami C Bond, David G Streets, Kristen F Yarber, Sibyl M Nelson, Jung-Hun Woo, and Zbigniew Klimont. A technology-based global inventory of black and organic carbon emissions from combustion. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres (1984–2012)*, 109(D14), 2004.

- [54] Guido Van Rossum et al. Python programming language. In *USENIX Annual Technical Conference*, volume 41, 2007.
- [55] Greet Janssens-Maenhout, VP Diego, and G Marilena Muntean. Global emission inventories in the emission database for global atmospheric research (EDGAR)—Manual (I). *Gridding: EDGAR emissions distribution on global gridmaps*, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2013.
- [56] Medhavi Gupta and Manju Mohan. Assessment of contribution to PM 10 concentrations from long range transport of pollutants using WRF-Chem over a subtropical urban airshed. *Atm spheric Pollution Research*, 2013.
- [57] EDGAR team. edgar.jrc.ec.europa.eu/htap_v2/index.php?secure=123. http://edgar.jrc.ec.europa.eu/htap_v2/index.php?SECURE=123. (Visited on 02/30/2015).
- [58] WU. Weather Forecast & reports - long range & local. <http://www.wunderground.com/>, 2015. (Visited on 03/21/2015).
- [59] Johannes Gerardus Jozef Olivier, AF Bouwman, JJM Berdowski, C Veldt, JPJ Bloos, AJH Visschedijk, PYJ Zandveld, JL Haverlag, et al. Description of EDGAR version 2.0: A set of global emission inventories of greenhouse gases and ozone-depleting substances for all anthropogenic and most natural sources on a per country basis and on 1 degree x 1 degree grid. 1996.
- [60] Yuh-Lang Lin, Richard D Farley, and Harold D Orville. Bulk parameterization of the snow field in a cloud model. *Journal of Climate and Applied Meteorology*, 22(6): 1065–1092, 1983.
- [61] Fei Chen and Jimy Dudhia. Coupling an advanced land surface-hydrology model with the Penn State-NCAR MM5 modeling system. part I: Model implementation and sensitivity. *Monthly Weather Review*, 129(4):569–585, 2001.
- [62] Song-You Hong and Jeong-Ock Jade Lim. The WRF single-moment 6-class microphysics scheme (WSM6). *Asia-Pacific Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, 42(2): 129–151, 2006.
- [63] John S Kain. The Kain-Fritsch convective parameterization: an update. *Journal of Applied Meteorology*, 43(1):170–181, 2004.
- [64] Eli J Mlawer, Steven J Taubman, Patrick D Brown, Michael J Iacono, and Shepard A Clough. Radiative transfer for inhomogeneous atmospheres: RRTM, a validated correlated-k model for the longwave. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres (1984–2012)*, 102(D14):16663–16682, 1997.
- [65] Mian Chin, Paul Ginoux, Stefan Kinne, Omar Torres, Brent N Holben, Bryan N Duncan, Randall V Martin, Jennifer A Logan, Akiko Higurashi, and Teruyuki Nakajima. Tropospheric aerosol optical thickness from the GOCART model and comparisons with satellite and sun photometer measurements. *Journal of the atmospheric sciences*, 59(3):461–483, 2002.
- [66] David C Carslaw and Karl Ropkins. Openair an R package for air quality data analysis. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 27:52–61, 2012.

- [67] Yang Zhang, Ping Liu, Betty Pun, and Christian Seigneur. A comprehensive performance evaluation of MM5-CMAQ for the summer 1999 Southern Oxidants Study episodePart I: Evaluation protocols, databases, and meteorological predictions. *Atmospheric Environment*, 40(26):4825–4838, 2006.
- [68] KH Schlüenzen and RS Sokhi. Overview of tools and methods for meteorological and air pollution mesoscale model evaluation and user training. *Joint report by WMO and COST*, 728, 2008.
- [69] Manju Mohan and Shweta Bhati. Analysis of WRF model performance over sub-tropical region of Delhi, India. *Advances in Meteorology*, pages 1–13, 2011.
- [70] Francesco Calabrese, Kristian Kloeckl, and Carlo Ratti. Wikicity: Real-time location-sensitive tools for the city. *Handbook of research on urban informatics: The practice and promise of the real-time city*, pages 390–413, 2008.
- [71] Jon Louis Bentley. Multidimensional binary search trees used for associative searching. *Communications of the ACM*, 18(9):509–517, 1975.
- [72] Matthew Kwan. *Visualization and analysis of mobile phone location data*. PhD thesis, RMIT University, 2012.
- [73] Ghoscher. Ghoscher’s blog. <http://ghoscher.me/2013/03/05/fuchs-maps/>, 2012. (Visited on 03/25/2015).
- [74] Using numpy and KD-trees with netCDF data. <http://nbviewer.ipython.org/github/Unidata/unidata-python-workshop/blob/master/netcdf-by-coordinates.ipynb>, 2012. (Visited on 03/25/2015).
- [75] Michal Cihar. Gammu. <http://wammu.eu/gammu/>. (Visited on 03/05/2015).